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The Impact of Social Media Usage on Students' Academic Performance

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Abstract. This study examined the relationship between social media usage and the academic performance of senior high school students at Buenavista Integrated School, Zamboanga City, during the 2025–2026 academic year. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study aimed to identify how engagement with platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok relates to students' academic outcomes. The total population of 277 students participated through a researcher-developed survey, with stratified random sampling ensuring representation across grade levels and academic strands. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation to assess usage patterns and their impact on General Weighted Average (GWA). Results indicate that students use social media moderately for both academic and social purposes. Platforms like Facebook and YouTube were primarily used for educational support, whereas Instagram and TikTok facilitated creative engagement and short-form learning. Statistical analysis revealed no significant correlation between social media usage and academic performance ($r = -0.109$, $p = 0.155$). Additionally, demographic factors including age, sex, and socioeconomic status did not significantly influence social media engagement. The findings suggest that moderate, purposeful use of social media coexists with satisfactory academic performance, highlighting the potential of digital platforms as supplementary learning tools when used responsibly. Implications include the promotion of digital literacy, integration of social media in pedagogical strategies, and guidance for students, educators, and parents on balanced online engagement to enhance learning outcomes.

Keywords: social media, academic performance, senior high school, descriptive-correlational study, digital literacy

Introduction

The rise of social media has transformed how people communicate, share information, and interact in the modern world. According to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), social media refers to web-based platforms built on Web 2.0 technology that enable users to create and exchange content interactively. Platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok allow instant communication and information sharing, making social media an essential part of daily life.

Academic performance, on the other hand, refers to a student's ability to apply skills, attitudes, and behaviors to achieve success in school (Hijazi & Naqvi, 2006). It reflects how effectively students perform in their academic tasks and responsibilities.

Previous studies have shown mixed findings regarding the relationship between social media use and academic performance. Ansari and Khan (2020) found that purposeful use of social media for academic discussions and resource sharing can improve learning outcomes. However, Ndaku (2013) reported that excessive social media use reduces study time, weakens grammar and spelling skills, and distracts students from academic responsibilities. These findings suggest that social media can either support or hinder academic success, depending on how it is used.

Despite numerous international studies, limited research has examined this issue within the local context of Buenavista Integrated School, Zamboanga City Division, Philippines. Differences in cultural background, behavioral patterns, and academic pressures may influence how social media affects students in this setting. Therefore, this study aimed to determine whether existing findings align with the experiences of students in Buenavista Integrated School.

This study was conducted among Grade 11 and Grade 12 students during the academic year 2025–2026. It sought to (1) identify the students' demographic profile, (2) determine the level of social media usage in terms of positive and negative impacts, (3) assess students' academic performance based on their General Weighted Average (GWA), and (4) examine whether social media has significant relationship to academic performance, and (5) whether demographic factors has significant differences to social media usage.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the impact of social media on the academic performance of Senior High School students (Grade 11-12).

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Socioeconomic status
2. What is the extent of social media usage among students in terms of its positive and negative impact through the following platforms?
 - 2.1 Facebook
 - 2.2 YouTube
 - 2.3 Instagram
 - 2.4 TikTok
3. What is the extent of academic performance among students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between social media usage and academic performance among students?
5. Is there a significant difference between the demographic profile and social media usage among student in terms of positive and negative impact through the following platforms:
 - 5.1 Facebook
 - 5.2 YouTube
 - 5.3 Instagram
 - 5.4 TikTok

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study examined the impact of social media usage on the academic performance of senior high school students. It focused on Grade 11 and Grade 12 students at Buenavista Integrated School, Zamboanga City Division, Philippines, during the academic year 2025–2026. The study had several limitations. First, it relied on self-reported data, which may have been influenced by response bias. Second, it only considered selected social media platforms—Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok—and excluded other digital platforms. Third, it did not examine other factors that may affect academic performance, such as personal motivation and teaching methods. The demographic profile included students aged 15 to 21 years and above, both male and female, from high, middle, and low socioeconomic backgrounds. These limitations helped narrow the focus of the study while providing insights into how social media usage affects the academic performance of this specific group of students.

Literature Review

Age

Foreign and local studies show that age influences how students use social media and how it impacts their academic performance. Foreign studies (Ahn, 2011; Chen et al., 2021) found that younger adolescents tend to use social media mainly for entertainment and social interaction, which often leads to distraction, reduced study time, and lower academic performance. Older students, however, are more likely to use social media for communication, collaboration, and academic purposes, resulting in more positive outcomes. Similarly, local studies (Hermes Jr. et al., 2019; Dimacangun & Guillena, 2023) revealed that younger students

are more vulnerable to negative effects due to limited self-control and time management skills. However, among senior high students, age was sometimes found to have no significant relationship with academic performance (Asanji, 2024). Overall, age influences patterns of social media use, but its impact on academic performance depends more on maturity, self-regulation, and purpose of use rather than age alone.

Sex

Foreign research (Alnjadat et al., 2019) found that female students often use social media for communication and academic collaboration, leading to positive outcomes, while male students tend to use it more for gaming and entertainment, which may negatively affect performance. However, local studies (Hermes Jr. et al., 2019; Dimacangun & Guillena, 2023) found no significant relationship between sex and academic performance. Both male and female students experienced positive and negative effects depending on how they used social media. While males and females may differ in how they use social media, sex alone does not significantly determine academic performance. The purpose and frequency of use are more important factors.

Socioeconomic status

Foreign studies (Chen et al., 2021) showed that students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds are more likely to use the internet and social media for educational purposes, leading to better academic performance. Those from lower SES backgrounds often use it for entertainment, which may negatively affect their studies. Local findings are mixed. Hermes Jr. et al. (2019) found that low-income students were more vulnerable to negative academic impacts due to limited supervision and resources. However, Dimacangun and Guillena (2023) found no significant relationship between SES and academic performance, though higher-SES students had better access to technology. SES influences access to digital resources and opportunities, but academic outcomes still depend largely on how students use social media.

Social Media

Social media platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok are widely used for communication, content sharing, and collaboration (Alalwan, 2022). Foreign and local studies agree that these platforms can support learning by promoting peer interaction, access to resources, and flexible learning opportunities (Ansari & Khan, 2020; Arago, 2025). However, excessive or non-academic use leads to distraction, procrastination, poor sleep, absenteeism, and lower academic performance (Junco, 2012; Wang et al., 2023; Cruz et al., 2023). Social media has a dual impact. When used responsibly for academic purposes, it enhances learning. When used excessively for entertainment, it negatively affects academic performance.

Facebook

Facebook was originally launched in 2004 by Mark Zuckerberg and has become one of the most widely used platforms among students. Studies show that Facebook supports collaborative learning, communication, and academic discussions (Ajjan & Hartshorne, 2008; Cabbigat, 2019). However, excessive use is associated with distraction, reduced study time, and poor sleep habits, which negatively affect academic performance (Junco, 2012; Wang et al., 2023). Facebook can be an effective supplementary learning tool when used academically, but overuse for socializing and entertainment can harm academic performance.

YouTube

YouTube, established in 2005, is widely used for both entertainment and education. Research shows that educational videos improve understanding, engagement, and test performance (Bonk, 2011; Caratiquit, 2022). However, heavy entertainment consumption and late-night viewing can lead to distraction, procrastination, and sleep deprivation, negatively affecting academic outcomes (Junco, 2012; Kosola et al., 2024). YouTube enhances academic performance when used for educational content but negatively impacts students when used excessively for entertainment.

Instagram

Instagram is widely used for communication and information sharing. Studies show that it can provide access to educational materials and peer support (Balani et al., 2025; Lactawan et al., 2024). However, excessive use may lead to addiction, distraction, reduced study time, and poor sleep habits (Blas et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2023). Instagram offers academic and social benefits, but balanced use is necessary to prevent negative academic consequences.

TikTok

TikTok, launched in 2016 by ByteDance, has become highly popular among students. Research shows that TikTok can support creativity, motivation, and even language learning (Zhen et al., 2022; Alimpos et al., 2023). However, its short-form, highly engaging content encourages excessive scrolling, which may lead to procrastination, sleep disruption, and poor academic performance (Paul et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2023).

TikTok can promote engagement and creative learning, but uncontrolled use may negatively affect study habits and academic performance.

Academic Performance

Both foreign and local studies agree that social media's impact on academic performance depends on usage patterns. Students who use platforms for academic collaboration, research, and communication experience neutral to positive outcomes (Bhandarkar et al., 2021; Dimacangun & Guillena, 2023). In contrast, students who use social media mainly for entertainment, especially during study time or late at night, experience distraction, lower grades, absenteeism, and poor time management (Chandrasena et al., 2022; Lomibao, 2024). Academic performance is not directly determined by social media use alone. Instead, the purpose, frequency, time management, and self-regulation of students are the key factors that determine whether social media use results in positive or negative academic outcomes.

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the relationship between students' social media use and their academic performance. According to Creswell (2014), correlational research examines the relationship between variables without manipulating them. In this study, the researchers aimed to identify whether patterns of social media use were related to the academic performance of senior high school students. A researcher-made survey questionnaire was used to collect data. Babbie (2020) explained that surveys are an effective way to gather quantitative data from a specific group, especially students. To ensure fair representation across grade levels and academic strands, stratified random sampling was applied. Etikan et al. (2016) stated that proper sampling methods help reduce bias and ensure that participants accurately represent the population. The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between variables. Field (2018) noted that correlational analysis is suitable for non-experimental studies that aim to describe relationships between measurable variables. Throughout the study, ethical standards were followed, including informed consent, confidentiality, voluntary participation, and adherence to research guidelines set by the American Psychological Association (APA, 2020).

Sampling Design

In this study, purposive sampling was used to select students who were relevant to the research, particularly those enrolled in the identified academic strands. At the same time, total enumeration was applied, meaning that all senior high school students were included as respondents. Instead of choosing only a sample, the entire population of 227 students participated in the study. This ensured complete representation of all strands and grade levels and allowed the data to reflect the overall perspective of the population.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Buenavista Integrated School in the Zamboanga City Division during the academic year 2025–2026. The school offers both Junior and Senior High School programs, including strands such as HUMSS, GAS, and TVL. It was selected as the research site because of its diverse student population and the increasing use of mobile devices and internet access among students, making social media a common part of their daily lives. Students in public secondary schools like Buenavista Integrated School often experience challenges in balancing technology use and academic responsibilities. The school setting provided a suitable background for examining how social media use relates to students' academic performance. Through this study, the researchers aimed to gain meaningful insights and promote responsible and productive use of digital platforms among students.

Research Participants

This study included all students in the Senior High School Department of Buenavista Integrated School. The total population of student-respondents was 277 across six selected grade levels and strands. The largest number of students (65) was in Grade 11- TVL, while the smallest number (20) was in Grade 12- HUMSS.

Research Instrument

The main instrument used in this study was a researcher-made questionnaire designed to gather information about the students' demographic profile, social media use, and academic performance. The questionnaire had three sections. The first section collected demographic information, including age, sex, and socioeconomic status. The second section focused on social media use, such as the platforms commonly used, the purpose of use (academic or entertainment), and signs of overuse. A four-point Likert scale was used: 4 – Strongly Agree (SA), 3 – Agree (A), 2 – Disagree (DA), and 1 – Strongly Disagree (SDA). The third section measured academic performance by asking students to provide their most recent General Weighted Average

(GWA). Permission was obtained from the research teacher before administering the questionnaire, and the study followed the Data Privacy Act of 2012 of the Republic of the Philippines to ensure confidentiality and protection of participants' information. To ensure validity and reliability, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts in education and research for content validation. It was also pilot-tested with 15 students from another grade level before the actual data collection.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the study, a letter of approval was secured from the school principal to allow data collection. Consent forms were given to the students and their parents or guardians, especially for minors, to ensure voluntary participation. After approval, the researcher distributed the questionnaires during scheduled class hours with the help of the class advisers to ensure proper distribution and collection. The completed questionnaires were collected immediately to achieve a high retrieval rate. Students' General Weighted Average (GWA) was also verified with the help of their advisers for those who gave consent. Finally, all collected data were organized, coded, and prepared for statistical analysis.

Results and Discussions

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile among students.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Students in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
15- 17 years old	124	17.7%
18- 20 years old	46	26.6%
21- above years old	3	1.7%
Total	173	100.0%

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the students in terms of age. The majority of the respondents are 18–20 years old (46 students or 26.6%), followed by those aged 15–17 years old, while only 3 students (1.7%) are 21 years old and above, out of 173 total respondents. This means that most of the students are in late adolescence to early adulthood, a stage where social media use is very common. According to Pew Research Center (2022), young adults aged 18–29 are among the most active social media users. This implies that the students in this study are highly exposed to social media, which may influence their academic performance either positively or negatively. The small percentage of students aged 21 and above (1.7%) shows that older students are less represented in the study. This means that the findings mainly reflect the experiences of younger students. Research by Junco (2012) found that time spent on social media can affect students' study habits and grades. Similarly, Kirschner and Karpinsk (2010) reported that heavy social media use is linked to lower academic performance. This implies that age is an important factor when examining the impact of social media on students' academic performance.

Table 2: Demographic Profile of the Students in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	58	33.5%
Female	115	66.5%
Total	173	100.0%

Table 2 shows the demographic profile of the students in terms of sex. Out of 173 respondents, 115 (66.5%) are female and 58 (33.5%) are male. This means that most of the participants in the study are female students. Therefore, the results about the impact of social media on academic performance mainly reflect the experiences of female students. According to the Pew Research Center (2022), both males and females actively use social media, but females tend to use social networking sites more for communication and interaction. Similarly, Lenhart and Amanda (2015) found that female adolescents are generally more engaged on social media than males. This means that female students may spend more time online, which can affect their academic performance either positively or negatively. In addition, Junco (2012) stated that time spent on social media is related to students' grades. This implies that sex is an important factor to consider when analyzing the impact of social media on students' academic performance.

Table 3: Demographic Profile of the Students in terms of Socioeconomic status

Socioeconomic status	Frequency	Percentage
Low- Income	162	93.6%
Middle- Income	9	5.2%
High- Income	2	1.2%
Total	173	100.0%

Table 3 shows the demographic profile of the students in terms of socioeconomic status. Out of 173 respondents, 162 (93.6%) are from low-income families, 9 (5.2%) are from middle-income families, and only 2 (1.2%) are from high-income families. This means that most of the students in the study come from low-income households. Therefore, the results about the impact of social media on academic performance mainly represent low-income students. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2018) stated that students from low-income families often depend on mobile phones and free online platforms for learning because they have limited access to paid resources. In addition, the Pew Research Center (2021) reported that lower-income households are more likely to rely on smartphones for internet access. This means that social media may serve as an important learning tool for these students. However, socioeconomic status is also linked to academic achievement (American Psychological Association, 2017). This implies that while social media can help low-income students access information, too much use may still affect their academic performance.

Problem 2: What is the extent of social media usage among students in terms of its positive and negative impact through the following platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok.

Table 4: The extent of social media usage among students in terms of the positive and negative impact through Facebook

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. I use Facebook to access educational content that helps me in my studies.	2.95	.62	Agree	Moderately Used
2. I join Facebook groups that help me understand my school lessons.	2.93	.62	Agree	Moderately Used
3. I use Facebook to communicate with my classmates about school requirements.	3.39	.54	Strongly Agree	Highly Used
4. Facebook helps me find useful learning materials for projects and assignments.	2.99	.60	Agree	Moderately Used
5. Facebook keeps me updated about school announcements and activities.	3.31	.56	Strongly Agree	Highly Used
6. I often get distracted from studying because I spend time scrolling in Facebook.	2.69	.73	Agree	Moderately Used
7. I sometimes forget to do my schoolwork because I focus too much on Facebook.	2.75	.76	Agree	Moderately Used
8. My late-night Facebook use makes me feel tired and less attentive in class.	2.82	.67	Agree	Moderately Used
9. I came late to school because I spent too much time at night scrolling in Facebook.	2.21	.73	Disagree	Fairly Used
10. I became absent from school because I spent too much time using Facebook.	1.97	.73	Disagree	Fairly Used
Over-all Mean	2.80		Agree	Moderately Used

Table 4 shows the extent of social media usage among students in terms of the positive and negative impact through Facebook. The two highest mean scores are using Facebook to communicate with classmates about school requirements (M = 3.39, SD = 0.54) and using Facebook to stay updated on school announcements and activities (M = 3.31, SD = 0.56). Both are verbally described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Highly Used. This means that students mainly use Facebook for academic communication, such as coordinating tasks and sharing reminders. Studies by Junco (2012) show that Facebook can support academic engagement when used for collaboration. This implies that academic use of social media can help students stay connected and informed, which may support their academic performance. On the other hand, the lowest mean scores are being absent from school because of too much Facebook use (M = 1.97, SD = 0.73) and coming late due to late-night scrolling (M = 2.21, SD = 0.73). Both are described as Disagree and interpreted as Fairly Used. This means that excessive Facebook use rarely leads to serious problems like absenteeism or tardiness. Research by Rosen et al. (2013) and Paul et al. (2012) suggests that the negative effects of social media depend more on self-control and intensity of use. This implies that social media alone does not automatically result in poor academic performance.

Table 5: The extent of social media usage among students in terms of the positive and negative impact through YouTube

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. I watch YouTube videos that help me understand academic lessons.	2.95	.62	Agree	Moderately Used
2. YouTube tutorials help me complete my assignments more effectively.	2.93	.62	Agree	Moderately Used
3. I use YouTube to review topics discussed in class.	3.39	.54	Strongly Agree	Highly Used
4. YouTube provides educational discussions that support my studying.	2.99	.60	Agree	Moderately Use
5. YouTube helps me develop skills useful for my school tasks.	3.31	.56	Strongly Agree	Highly Used
6. I sometimes skip studying because I spend too much time watching YouTube.	2.69	.73	Agree	Moderately Used
7. YouTube distracts me from focusing on my school responsibilities.	2.75	.76	Agree	Moderately Used
8. Staying up late watching YouTube makes me feel sleepy at class.	2.82	.67	Agree	Moderately Used
9. I came late to school because I spend too much time watching YouTube at night.	2.21	.73	Disagree	Fairly Used
10. I became absent from school because I spent too much time watching YouTube.	1.97	.73	Disagree	Fairly Used
Over-all Mean	2.80		Agree	Moderately Used

Table 5 shows the extent of social media usage among students in terms of the positive and negative impact through YouTube. The two highest mean scores are using YouTube to review topics discussed in class ($M = 3.39$, $SD = 0.54$) and using it to develop skills useful for school tasks ($M = 3.31$, $SD = 0.56$). Both are described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as Highly Used. This means that students mainly use YouTube as a learning support tool to better understand lessons and improve their academic skills. Studies by Kay (2012) and Moghavvemi, Sedigheh et al. (2018) found that educational videos on YouTube can improve learning and academic engagement. This implies that when used for educational purposes, YouTube can help strengthen academic performance. On the other hand, the lowest mean scores are being absent from school because of watching too much YouTube ($M = 1.97$, $SD = 0.73$) and coming late due to late-night viewing ($M = 2.21$, $SD = 0.73$). Both are described as Disagree and interpreted as Fairly Used. This means that excessive YouTube use rarely causes serious problems like absenteeism or tardiness. Research by Rosen et al. (2013) and Andrew et al. (2015) explains that negative effects depend more on self-control and purpose of use. This implies that YouTube use alone does not automatically lead to poor academic performance.

Table 6: The extent of social media usage among students in terms of the positive and negative impact through Instagram

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. I follow educational pages on Instagram that help me academically.	2.81	.65	Agree	Moderately Used
2. Instagram gives me creative ideas that I use in school tasks.	2.88	.63	Agree	Moderately Used
3. Instagram helps me stay informed about school reminders and events.	2.61	.68	Agree	Moderately Used
4. Educational content on Instagram motivates me to study.	2.79	.65	Agree	Moderately Used
5. I use Instagram to collaborate with my classmates regarding school activities.	2.62	.67	Agree	Moderately Used
6. I spend time on Instagram even when I should be studying.	2.39	.69	Disagree	Fairly Used
7. I lose focus on school tasks because I keep checking Instagram.	2.20	.70	Disagree	Fairly Used
8. Staying up late scrolling on Instagram makes me feel tired in class.	2.34	.75	Disagree	Fairly Used
9. I came late to school because I used Instagram late at night.	2.08	.71	Disagree	Fairly Used
10. I became absent from school because I spent too much time using Instagram.	1.99	.73	Disagree	Fairly Used
Over-All Mean	2.47		Disagree	Fairly Used

Table 6 shows the extent of social media usage among students in terms of the positive and negative impact through Instagram. The two highest mean scores are “Instagram gives me creative ideas for school tasks” (M = 2.88, SD = 0.63) and “I follow educational pages on Instagram that help me academically” (M = 2.81, SD = 0.65). Both are described as Agree and interpreted as Moderately Used. This means that students use Instagram mainly for creative ideas and additional learning materials, not as their main study tool. Studies by Manca et al (2016), and Alhabash et al (2017) show that Instagram can support creativity and student engagement when used for educational purposes. This implies that moderate and purposeful use of Instagram can positively support learning. On the other hand, the lowest mean score is “I became absent from school because I spent too much time using Instagram” (M = 1.99, SD = 0.73), described as Disagree and interpreted as Fairly Used. Other negative effects, such as coming late or losing focus, are also low. This means that Instagram rarely causes serious academic problems like absenteeism. Research by Junco (2012) and Rosen, (2013) explains that negative academic effects usually happen with excessive use, not moderate use. This implies that Instagram use alone does not automatically lead to poor academic performance.

Table 7: The extent of social media usage among students in terms of the positive and negative impact through TikTok

	Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1.	I watch TikTok videos that explain academic topics in simple ways.	3.13	.61	Agree	Moderately Used
2.	TikTok provides short educational content that helps me understand lessons.	3.12	.58	Agree	Moderately Used
3.	I learn study techniques and tips from TikTok educational creators.	3.10	.55	Agree	Moderately Used
4.	TikTok helps me discover useful academic resources.	3.02	.60	Agree	Moderately Used
5.	Watching educational TikTok videos motivates me to study.	3.01	.59	Agree	Moderately Used
6.	I ignore my school tasks because I spend too much time on TikTok.	2.21	.64	Disagree	Fairly Used
7.	I get distracted from my assignments because I keep checking TikTok.	2.34	.71	Disagree	Fairly Used
8.	Staying up late using TikTok makes me feel tired or less active in class.	2.41	.75	Disagree	Fairly Used
9.	I came late to school because I stayed up late scrolling on TikTok.	2.16	.73	Disagree	Fairly Used
10.	I became absent from school because I spent too much time using TikTok.	1.97	.72	Disagree	Fairly Used
	Over-All Mean	2.65		Agree	Moderately Used

Table 7 shows the extent of social media usage among students in terms of the positive and negative impact through TikTok. The two highest mean scores are “watching TikTok videos that explain academic topics in simple ways” (M = 3.13, SD = 0.61) and “TikTok provides short educational content that helps me understand lessons” (M = 3.12, SD = 0.58). Both are described as Agree and interpreted as Moderately Used. This means that students use TikTok as a supplementary learning tool, with short and engaging videos that make complex topics easier to understand. Studies by Wei et al. (2021) and Guo et al. (2014) show that short-form educational videos can improve engagement, motivation, and comprehension. This implies that purposeful use of TikTok can positively support academic performance. In contrast, the lowest mean score is “I became absent from school because I spent too much time using TikTok” (M = 1.97, SD = 0.72), described as Disagree and interpreted as Fairly Used. Other negative indicators, such as being late or distracted, are also low. This means that TikTok rarely causes serious academic problems like absenteeism. Research by Andrew et al. (2015) and Rosen et al. (2014) explains that negative academic effects mostly occur with excessive use and poor self-regulation. This implies that students can generally manage their TikTok use without it harming their school performance.

Table 8: Summary of the extents of social media usage among students in terms of the positive and negative impact through Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Facebook	2.80	Moderately Used
YouTube	2.66	Moderately Used
Instagram	2.47	Fairly Used
TikTok	2.65	Moderately Used
Over-All Mean	2.65	Moderately Used

Table 8 shows the summary of social media usage among students across Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok in terms of positive and negative impacts. Facebook had a mean of 2.80 (Moderately Used), indicating that students use it for both academic and non-academic purposes, such as communicating with classmates, accessing learning materials, and receiving school updates. YouTube had a mean of 2.66 (Moderately Used), showing that students use it as a supplementary learning tool to review lessons, watch tutorials, and understand academic topics. TikTok had a mean of 2.65 (Moderately Used), suggesting that students engage with short educational videos and study-related content while keeping usage under control. This means that students use these platforms in a balanced way, supporting both learning and leisure without seriously affecting their academic responsibilities. In contrast, Instagram had a mean of 2.47 (Fairly Used), indicating that it is used less frequently for academic purposes and more for social interaction and entertainment. The overall mean of 2.65 (Moderately Used) reflects a moderate level of social media usage among students across all platforms. This means that social media is part of students' daily lives but not to an excessive extent that would harm academic performance. These results imply that students are generally able to manage their social media use, balancing academic demands with online engagement. This aligns with research showing that moderate and purposeful use of social media can support learning without causing major academic problems (Junco 2012; Rosen et al., 2013).

Problem 3: What is the academic performance of the students.

Table 9: Academic Performance of the Students for 2nd Quarter, School Year 2025-2026.

Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
General Weighted Average Grade	85.65	5.61	Very Satisfactory

Table 9 shows the academic performance of the students for the 2nd Quarter of School Year 2025–2026, measured using the General Weighted Average (GWA). The results reveal a mean GWA of 85.65, which is verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This means that, on average, students performed well academically and met the expected learning standards across their subjects. A mean GWA of 85.65 suggests consistent effort and satisfactory understanding of lessons during the second quarter. According to the grading legend, a GWA of 85–89 falls under the Very Satisfactory level, indicating that students showed strong academic competence, though there is still room to improve toward an Outstanding level. This implies that the students' learning outcomes during this period were generally positive and aligned with the school's academic expectations.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between social media usage and academic performance among students.

Table 10: Significant relationship between the social media usage among students in terms of its positive and negative impact and academic performance among students

Variances		R-value	P-value	Interpretation
X Social Media Usage	Y Academic Performance	1 -.109	.155 .155	Not Significant

Table 10 shows the relationship between social media usage and academic performance among students. The correlation coefficient ($r = -0.109$) indicates a very weak negative relationship. This means that as social media use slightly increases, academic performance decreases only minimally. However, the relationship is extremely weak and practically negligible. In educational research, correlations near zero suggest little to no linear relationship between variables (Cohen, 1988; Schober et al 2018). This implies that students' academic performance is not significantly affected by social media use, as other factors like study habits, motivation, and teaching quality are likely more important. The p-value of 0.155 is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This means the relationship between social media usage and academic performance is not statistically significant. When $p > .05$, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis (Field, 2018; Gravetter & Wallnau, 2017). Therefore, the study accepts the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between social media usage and academic performance. This supports earlier findings showing that students use Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok at moderate levels without it seriously affecting their academic outcomes. This implies that students are generally able to balance social media use with their school responsibilities.

Problem 5: : Is there a significant difference between the demographic profile and social media usage among students.

Table 11: Significant difference between the demographic profile (age) and social media usage among students

Variances		F-value	P-value	Interpretation
X Social Media Usage	Y Age	.891	.412	Not Significant

Table 11 shows the difference in social media usage among students based on age. The computed F-value of 0.891 indicates very little variation in usage across different age groups. This means that students, regardless of age, use platforms like Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok in similar ways for both positive and negative purposes. In statistical analysis, a low F-value suggests that differences between group means are small compared to variability within groups (Field, 2018; Gravetter & Wallnau, 2017). This implies that age does not significantly affect how students engage with social media. The p-value of 0.412 is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This means there is no statistically significant difference between age and social media usage. When $p > .05$, the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating insufficient evidence to claim a significant difference (Cohen, 1988; Field, 2018). Therefore, the hypothesis that age does not significantly influence social media usage is accepted. This reinforces the idea that students across different age groups experience similar effects from social media, whether positive or negative. This implies that age alone does not determine how social media affects students' academic behaviors.

Table 12: Significant difference between the demographic profile (sex) and social media usage among students

Variances	Sex	Mean	T-value	P-value	Interpretation
X Social Media Usage and Sex	Y Male	2.71	2.117	.518	Not Significant
	Female	2.61	2.025		

Table 12 shows the difference in social media usage between male and female students. Male students had a mean of 2.71, while female students had a mean of 2.61, both interpreted as Moderately Used. The computed t-values (2.117 for males and 2.025 for females) indicate only a small difference between the two groups. This means that although males use social media slightly more than females, the difference is minimal, and both groups generally use Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok at a comparable and moderate level. Research suggests that while males and females may differ in the purposes for using social media, the overall intensity of use is often similar among students in the same academic setting (Muscanell & Guadagno, 2012; Dhir et al., 2017). This implies that sex does not strongly influence how much students use social media. The p-value of 0.518 is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This means the difference in mean social media usage between males and females is not statistically significant and may have occurred by chance. When $p > .05$, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis (Field, 2018; Gravetter & Wallnau, 2017). Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in social media usage based on sex is accepted. This implies that male and female students generally use and experience social media in similar ways without meaningful differences in impact.

Table 13: Significant difference between the demographic profile (socioeconomic status) and social media usage among students

Variances		F-value	P-value	Interpretation
X Social Media Usage	Y Socioeconomic status	.722	.487	Not Significant

Table 13 shows the difference in social media usage among students based on socioeconomic status. The computed F-value of 0.722 indicates very little variation in usage among low-, middle-, and high-income students. This means that students, regardless of income, use Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok in similar ways for both positive and negative purposes. In ANOVA, a low F-value suggests that differences between group means are small compared to variability within groups (Field, 2018; Gravetter & Wallnau, 2017). This implies that socioeconomic status does not significantly affect how students use social media, likely because affordable devices and internet access make these platforms widely accessible. The p-value of 0.487 is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This means there is no statistically significant difference between socioeconomic status and social media usage. When $p > .05$, the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating insufficient evidence to claim a significant difference (Cohen, 1988; Field, 2018). Therefore, the hypothesis that socioeconomic status does not affect social media usage is accepted. This implies that students across different income levels experience similar effects of social media, and its academic-related impacts are generally uniform regardless of socioeconomic background.

Ethical Considerations

The study followed the ethical principle of beneficence, ensuring that participants benefited from the research while minimizing any risks. Students were informed how the study could help understand social media's impact on academic performance. Participation was voluntary, and students could skip any questions they were uncomfortable with. The researchers reported results honestly and avoided manipulating data. Respect for participants' dignity and autonomy was maintained throughout. These steps ensured the study followed ethical research standards.

Conclusion

The study concluded that social media usage does not have a significant impact on students' academic performance. Students use platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok at a level that does not interfere with their schoolwork. Social media serves both educational and social purposes, and students are generally able to balance these effectively. Demographic factors such as age, sex, and socioeconomic status do not significantly affect how students use social media or its impact. Regardless of these differences, students experience similar positive and negative effects from these platforms. This suggests that social media has become a normal part of students' academic and daily lives. Overall, the study concludes that moderate and purposeful use of social media can coexist with satisfactory academic performance, and problems only arise from excessive or unmanaged use.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it is recommended that school administrators develop programs and policies that promote digital literacy, responsible online behavior, and awareness of both the positive and negative effects of social media. Teachers should thoughtfully integrate platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok into their instructional strategies to enhance student engagement, collaboration, and access to learning resources. Students are encouraged to continue using social media responsibly and in moderation by prioritizing academic tasks and managing their time to minimize distractions and fatigue. Parents and guardians should provide guidance and support by monitoring online activities and reinforcing healthy study habits at home. Furthermore, future researchers are advised to explore additional factors such as screen time, study habits, and psychological influences to gain a deeper understanding of the long-term impact of social media on students' academic performance.

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